

Europium doped YBO₃ luminescent pigment for security ink application

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Abstract

Herein, we report an orange-red colour emitting YBO₃:Eu³⁺ phosphor, synthesized by Sol gel technique, which can be simply scaled up in large quantity. This highly luminescent and optically active YBO₃:Eu³⁺ phosphor with average particle size in the range from 100 to 120 nm provides emission at 591 nm upon 245 nm excitation wavelength and also excitable in range of 280-480nm excitation wavelengths. The structural/microstructural and photoluminescence behaviour were characterized by scanning electron microscopy, transmission electron microscopy/high-resolution transmission electron microscopy and fluorescent spectroscopy, respectively. Further, this nanophosphor was used to design luminescent security ink with commercially available polyvinyl chloride gold medium for printing of highly uniform security codes as investigated by PL mapping instrument. Thus, this facile method to synthesize a low cost YBO₃:Eu³⁺ phosphor based security ink offers a nonreplicable security codes for printing that can be easily printed but is difficult to duplicate.